

ISic0051

I.Sicily inscription 0051

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) · M(anibus) · s(acrum)

2. P(ublius) · Edusius · Ba

3. silides · vix(it)

4. ann(os) · · XXXXV

Apparatus

Text of

Translation (eng)

Sacred to the Spirits of the Underworld. Pyblius Edusius Basilides; he lived forty-five years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175717

EDR 076313

EDCS 9400439

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1975.0452

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 52

Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 267 no.36

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